

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19894296

DEVELOPING TOURISM IN THE MEKONG DELTA, VIETNAM

Do Huong Lan¹, Nguyen Tan Hung² and Tran Thi Hai Yen³

¹University of Finance - Marketing, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; Email: dhlan@ufm.edu.vn; Orcid ID: 0009-0009-9180-295X

²University of Finance - Marketing, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; Corresponding author, Email: nt.hung@ufm.edu.vn; Orcid ID: 0009-0005-4279-8684

³University of Finance - Marketing, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam; Email: tranthihaiyen@ufm.edu.vn

Received: 15/02/2026
Accepted: 18/03/2026

Corresponding Author: Nguyen Tan Hung
(nt.hung@ufm.edu.vn)

ABSTRACT

Tourism is considered a comprehensive economic sector because it is interdisciplinary, inter-regional and imbued with cultural and humanistic identity, as well as highly socialized. In terms of economic management, tourism is also a smokeless industry, based on natural, cultural and social factors and brings many profits, has a positive impact on economic development, job creation, expanding cultural exchange, international integration, enhancing national and local status. Therefore, tourism development of each country and each locality often rely on natural, cultural and social advantages to build and implement appropriate policies. This study analyzes the content of tourism development and factors directly affecting tourism development, including: (1) Natural, cultural and social conditions; (2) Local policies. The study is implemented in an experimental direction to evaluate the practical development of tourism in the Mekong Delta. The author builds a theoretical framework and surveys the opinions of 240 managers of 100 cultural and tourism organizations in 3/6 localities in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, including A Giang province, Tay Ninh province, Kien Giang province. The research and survey results are analyzed, evaluated, and verified by scientific methods, serving as a basis for drawing research conclusions and discussing the issue of tourism development policies in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam in the next period.

KEYWORDS: Tourism; Developing tourism; Mekong Delta; Vietnam.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vietnam is a country in Southeast Asia, with many advantages in natural, cultural and social conditions for tourism development: It has about 3,200 km of coastline, 700,000 km² of continental shelf with many islands and archipelagos such as Hoang Sa, Truong Sa, Phu Quoc, Con Son; The East Sea is part of the Pacific Ocean with an area of 3,447,000 km², the third largest sea among the seas on the Earth's surface (PN, 2005).

The terrain of Vietnam's mainland is divided into the North, Central and South. In which, the Mekong Delta in the South has flat terrain, diverse ecosystems; temperate climate, rich and unique community culture and many unique natural products; there are many pristine lands which are conditions for developing ecotourism (Mai, T.T.X., 2017). These are favorable natural, cultural and social conditions for the Mekong Delta to develop tourism with many types of tourism to serve the needs of tourists.

According to general assessment, tourism in the Mekong Delta region has had many positive changes in recent years, especially in promotion and connection with tourist centers outside the region; tourism activities have recovered well after the Covid-19 pandemic with many positive marks in revenue and number of visitors: In 2024, tourism in the Mekong Delta region welcomed over 52 million visitors, an increase of 15.9% over the same period in 2023, of which international visitors reached over 2.8 million, an increase of more than 49%; total revenue from tourism reached over 62000 billion VND, an increase of more than 36% over 2023 (VNAT, 2025).

However, the tourism development of the Mekong Delta is assessed and evaluated as not commensurate with the available potential and advantages, due to many objective and subjective factors. And according to the assessment of experts and managers: Tourism products of the Mekong Delta are not diverse and rich, have not promoted the values and resources of unique culture and nature, lack of specific tourism products with big brands of the region; in addition, the infrastructure system serving resorts, shopping, organizing cultural and sports events, conferences, seminars, exhibitions is still lacking and not synchronized; tourism human resources have not met the requirements in the new period (GN, 2025).

The above practices are raising management questions, attracting the attention of many experts, managers and researchers. In that context, the author conducts research with the desire to analyze and objectively evaluate the practice of tourism

development in the Mekong Delta to provide empirical information and imply appropriate policy contents.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The common concept of tourism today is the activity of traveling to a place other than the place of regular residence for a certain period of time for sightseeing, entertainment, relaxation, cultural learning or other legitimate purposes such as experiencing, exploring and connecting with new lands... According to Wikipedia (2025), tourism is traveling for pleasure or business purposes; it is also the theory and practice of organizing travel programs, the business of attracting, providing and entertaining tourists, and the business of tour operators.

Tourism plays an important role in the development of the country and locality. In terms of economy, tourism contributes significantly to GDP, creates jobs and attracts investment. In terms of society, tourism promotes exchange, understanding and cooperation between countries and people. In terms of culture, tourism contributes to preserving and promoting the cultural, historical and natural values of destinations. According to Hung, N.M. (2023), developing tourism into a spearhead economic sector creates a driving force for the development of other industries and fields, contributing to the formation of a modern economic structure. Therefore, tourism development is an important strategy and task often identified by countries and localities with advantages in tourism development to achieve economic, cultural and social development goals.

In many recent studies, tourism development is often emphasized as the development of tourism activities in a sustainable, professional, modern direction, associated with the preservation and promotion of cultural and natural values, while ensuring a balance of economic, social and environmental benefits. Sustainable tourism development requires the participation of the entire political system, businesses and the community, focusing on solutions such as policy development, investment in green tourism, resource protection, promoting digital transformation and creating high-quality tourism products. According to the interpretation of Ung, N.T. (2025), the sustainable development of the tourism industry has an organic and inseparable connection with the stability and development of society in localities and countries. This is the perspective of sustainable development in research and management of tourism development

to serve the strategic goals of the country and localities. In this study, the author approaches tourism development in the direction of sustainable tourism development, so the concept of tourism development is identified with the concept of sustainable tourism development.

Vietnam's 2017 Law on Tourism (VNA, 2017) stipulates: "Sustainable tourism development is tourism development that simultaneously meets socio-economic and environmental requirements, ensuring the harmony of interests of subjects participating in tourism activities, without harming the ability to meet tourism needs in the future" (Article 3). From this legal aspect, Hong, N.M. (2025) further explains that sustainable tourism development aims at the harmony between the three main pillars of economy, society and environment, and needs to regularly monitor and evaluate the impact of tourism activities to realize the goal of making tourism a spearhead economic sector of Vietnam. Similarly, Ung, N.T. (2025) explains the economic, social and environmental aspects in the goal of sustainable tourism development, which is to ensure sustainable livelihoods, create jobs and increase income for local communities; Preserve and promote local cultural values; promote the role of local communities; ensure fairness and social security; improve tourist satisfaction and quality of experience...

From the theoretical, legal and practical aspects, the above studies refer to the content and core of tourism development. In this study, the author determines the scope of research on tourism development associated with local development management - Mekong Delta, Vietnam. Therefore, the contents of tourism development are interpreted in general in association with the issue of local development management; the scale "Developing tourism" (DT) is designed to imply the main contents, including: Tourism development promotes local economic growth (creates jobs, increases income for local communities; ensures fairness and social security) [DT1]; Tourism development contributes to preserving and promoting local cultural values (promotes the role of the local community in preserving and promoting cultural values) [DT2]; Tourism development contributes to preserving and promoting the value of natural heritage, contributes to protecting the environment, protecting heritage, and does not harm the ability to meet future tourism needs [DT3].

In essence, local tourism development is based on the advantages of natural conditions, culture and society of residents; at the same time, tourism

development is based on the foundation promoted by local policies. Many recent studies have affirmed and analyzed in depth the natural, cultural and social conditions of residents and local tourism development policies in the sense that these factors are both the foundation, the conditions for formation, and have a direct impact on tourism development.

2.1. Natural, Cultural and Social Conditions

In practical terms, natural, cultural and social conditions are the foundation for tourism development in a locality. Minh, L.V. (2022) affirmed that nature, terrain, climate, water and organisms are tourism resources - an important factor affecting tourism development and one of the factors that make up tourism products. The specific nature of tourism resources (uniqueness, attractiveness, uniqueness...) is one of the factors that make a difference, creating specific tourism products for each country, each locality, each tourist destination. In addition, cultural and social factors are also affirmed by Minh, L.V. (2022), including historical and revolutionary cultural relics; festivals; traditional craft villages; national cultural and artistic values and the participation of local communities where tourism resources are located. On this issue, Duc, L.Q. (2012) generalized that cultural factors imply cultural resources, expressed in human resources and cultural products that have the meaning of promoting tourism economic development. Similarly, Hung, T.V. (2024) argued that human resource development and cultural product development are important contents to realize the goal of developing cultural resources and promoting tourism development.

In the most general way, the studies of Duc, L.Q. (2012), Minh, L.V. (2022) and Hung, T.V., (2024) have interpreted the content of the Natural, cultural and social conditions as an objective condition for tourism development in each locality. The scale "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC) was built to imply the main contents: The locality has unique and attractive natural conditions (nature, terrain, climate, rivers, ecosystems, etc.) favorable for tourism development [NC1]; The locality has many unique heritages (historical and revolutionary cultural relics; festivals; traditional craft villages; national cultural and artistic values), favorable for tourism development [NC2]; Local people are active participants in local tourism development (have understanding of culture and tourism; have knowledge and skills to protect, exploit and promote community cultural values; have awareness, attitude and responsibility to preserve and promote

community cultural values) [NC3].

2.2. Local Policies

Minh, L.V. (2022) analyzed and affirmed that tourism development policy is the key to success or failure in local tourism development; tourism development policy mechanisms affect all tourism activities from exploitation and protection of tourism resources to human resource training, investment, tourism planning, and business activities in the tourism sector. Accordingly, when localities have the right and appropriate policies, they will have favorable conditions to promote tourism development, bringing high efficiency and sustainability. For example, localities with open policies, with specific and attractive mechanisms in tourism development will stimulate investors, attract tourists, and create conditions for the tourism industry to develop; with policies to protect and promote cultural and heritage values, they will always proactively have resources for tourism development; otherwise, it will hinder the development of the tourism industry....

Sharing the same view, Thu, N.T.H. (2025) emphasized that sustainable tourism policy is not only limited to the field of state management but also a tool to guide the participation of relevant actors, including businesses, communities and tourists. When localities have good policies, tourism development will be favorable and contribute a lot to the growth target. Specifically: Social policies aim to create jobs, increase community participation, preserve and promote cultural values; environmental policies focus on protecting resources, minimizing negative impacts, encouraging green and ecological tourism models; governance policies with the goal of improving institutions, enhancing management capacity, promoting public-private partnership, regional linkages and international cooperation...

The common problem in the research perspective of Minh, L.V. (2022) and Thu, N.T.H. (2025), is that Local Policy is a subjective condition arising from the

administrative activities of local government agencies, which affects tourism development. The scale "Local policies" (LP) is designed to imply some main contents: Localities effectively implement policies to conserve and exploit the value of natural resources (nature, terrain, climate, rivers, ecosystems, etc.) to achieve the goal of environmental protection and proactively obtain resources for tourism development [LP1]; Localities effectively implement policies to conserve and exploit the value of heritages (historical and revolutionary cultural relics; festivals; traditional craft villages; national cultural and artistic values) to achieve the goal of cultural development and proactively obtain resources for tourism development [LP2]; Localities implement policies to propagate and educate people to be aware, behave in a standard manner, promote the value of heritage, culture and protect natural resources, and become active subjects to achieve the goal of local tourism development [LP3].

Through the general study on tourism development, it can be seen that each locality relies on the advantages of natural conditions, culture and society to issue appropriate policies to develop tourism and promote growth targets. Therefore, in terms of theory and practice, the natural, cultural and social conditions of residents and the local tourism development policy are factors that are both the foundation and conditions for formation and have a direct impact on tourism development. With the above explanation, this study puts forward the hypothesis: *Natural, cultural and social conditions (H1), Local policies (H2) are important resources that directly affect local tourism development.*

Based on the inheritance and development of the results of many previous studies, the author built a theoretical framework with a model consisting of 3 scales and 9 observation variables. These observation variables were designed into a survey form with 9 corresponding questions and measured by a 5-level Likert scale: 1 - Strongly disagree; 2 - Disagree; 3 - No opinion; 4 - Agree; 5 - Strongly agree (Table 1, Figure 1).

Table 1: Theoretical Framework.

No	Scales	Encode	Rating levels				
			1	2	3	4	5
I	Natural, cultural and social conditions	NC					
1	The locality has unique and attractive natural conditions (nature, terrain, climate, rivers, ecosystems, etc.) favorable for tourism development	NC1					
2	The locality has many unique heritages (historical and revolutionary cultural relics; festivals; traditional craft villages; national cultural and artistic values), favorable for tourism development	NC2					

3	Local people are active participants in local tourism development (have understanding of culture and tourism; have knowledge and skills to protect, exploit and promote community cultural values; have awareness, attitude and responsibility to preserve and promote community cultural values)	NC3					
II	Local policies	LP					
4	Localities effectively implement policies to conserve and exploit the value of natural resources (nature, terrain, climate, rivers, ecosystems, etc.) to achieve the goal of environmental protection and proactively obtain resources for tourism development	LP1					
5	Localities effectively implement policies to conserve and exploit the value of heritages (historical and revolutionary cultural relics; festivals; traditional craft villages; national cultural and artistic values) to achieve the goal of cultural development and proactively obtain resources for tourism development	LP2					
6	Localities implement policies to propagate and educate people to be aware, behave in a standard manner, promote the value of heritage, culture and protect natural resources, and become active subjects to achieve the goal of local tourism development	LP3					
III	Developing tourism	DT					
7	Tourism development promotes local economic growth (creates jobs, increases income for local communities; ensures fairness and social security)	DT1					
8	Tourism development contributes to preserving and promoting local cultural values (promotes the role of the local community in preserving and promoting cultural values)	DT2					
9	Tourism development contributes to preserving and promoting the value of natural heritage, contributes to protecting the environment, protecting heritage, and does not harm the ability to meet future tourism needs	DT3					

Source: Compiled By the Author Through the Review

2.3. Research Model

Figure 1: Research Model.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

- Qualitative research: Conducted through the collection and analysis of secondary data, including many published documents, from which the author built a theoretical research framework with 3 scales: "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) and "Developing tourism" (DT) [Table 1, Figure 1].

- Quantitative research: Conducted through collecting and analyzing primary data in the form of a survey of 240 managers of 100 tourism organizations in 3/6 localities in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, including An Giang province, Tay Ninh province, Kien Giang province.

With the data collected through the survey, the author conducted exploratory factor analysis and multivariate regression analysis to test the research model and hypothesis. According to Hair, J.F. et al. (2009), the minimum sample size required for exploratory factor analysis and regression analysis for

the 3-scale model and 9 observed variables of this study is $N = 9 \times 5 = 45$.

In fact, the author conducted an official survey with a sample of $N = 240$ managers of 100 tourism organizations ($N > 45$), ensuring reliability when conducting empirical research. The survey was conducted selectively: Respondents were those with 2 years or more of management experience in the tourism sector; the survey was conducted with the consent of the respondents after the author conducted a preliminary interview. The survey results collected 240/240 valid responses, achieving a valid response rate of 100%.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on survey data collected from 240 tourism organization managers, the author tested the reliability of the scales and observed variables in the theoretical model. According to Hair, J.F. et al. (2009), the scales are reliable when meeting the standard

condition Cronbach's alpha > 0.6; the observed variables are reliable when meeting the standard condition Corrected Item-Total Correlation > 0.3. The

test results show that all 3 scales and 9 observed variables in the theoretical model are reliable (Table 2).

Table 2: Statistical Results and Testing Results of the Scale.

Scales	Observed variables	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach' Alpha	Corrected Item-Total Correlation
1. Natural, cultural and social conditions (NC)	NC1	240	1	5	4.22	.611	.688	NC1 = .484
	NC2	240	1	5	4.14	.568		NC2 = .506
	NC3	240	1	5	4.10	.634		NC3 = .523
2. Local policies (LP)	LP1	240	1	5	4.10	.651	.701	LP1 = .418
	LP2	240	1	5	4.04	.593		LP2 = .435
	LP3	240	1	5	4.01	.604		LP3 = .509
3. Developing tourism (DT)	DT1	240	1	5	4.12	.646	.694	DT1 = .601
	DT2	240	1	5	4.10	.617		DT2 = .588
	DT3	240	1	5	4.16	.597		DT3 = .579
Valid N (listwise)		240						

Source: Author's Survey Results

The statistical data in Table 2 shows that the observations of the scale "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP), "Developing tourism" (DT) are rated at an average level of Mean \geq 4.01, all of which are statistically significant according to the Likert scale (1-5). This shows the general opinion of tourism organization managers that localities in the Mekong Delta have favorable natural, cultural and social conditions for tourism development; local policies issued aim to preserve and exploit the value of natural resources, exploit the value of heritages, protect the environment and develop human resources for the purpose of tourism development. In terms of economy, localities developing tourism have created jobs, increased income for the community, promoted economic growth and ensured fairness and social security. In the social aspect, localities that develop tourism have promoted the role of local communities in preserving and promoting cultural values. In the environmental aspect, localities that develop tourism have contributed to preserving and promoting the value of natural heritage, contributing to protecting the environment and heritage, without harming the ability to meet future tourism needs.

However, there is a certain difference in the observed values of the scales. Specifically, the observed values of the "Local policies" (LP) scale are assessed at the lowest level with Mean (LP1) = 4.10, Mean (LP2) = 4.04, Mean (LP3) = 4.01, showing that the opinions of tourism organization managers underestimate the policies issued by the locality. Accordingly, in many specific locations, the conservation and exploitation of natural resource values, the exploitation of heritage values, environmental protection and human resource development for the purpose of tourism development have not been carried out with the expected results and efficiency. From a specific perspective, it can be seen that natural resources and

heritages, ethnic and community cultures are exploited, but there are still limitations in output - tourism products are not diverse and rich enough to meet the increasing needs of tourists; Propaganda and education work has been carried out, but it is still not effective in raising people's understanding, awareness and responsibility in preserving nature, exploiting heritages, ethnic cultures, and communities for the purpose of developing local tourism. The above problem has a direct impact on tourism development in localities in the Mekong Delta. Because tourism products are exploited in a diverse way; people are educated regularly and fully, they will have knowledge and responsibility to protect nature, protect heritages, ethnic cultures, and communities, at this time localities will have favorable conditions to develop tourism.

The research and survey results synthesized and analyzed above contribute to reflecting the tourism development practices of localities in the Mekong Delta, similar to the comments and assessments of some recent studies. Mai, T.T.X. (2017) analyzed the practices and commented, concluding that the Mekong Delta has a lot of potential for tourism development, however, the results of attracting and developing tourism have not been as expected, not commensurate with the potential; there is a lack of cultural products, gifts, souvenirs for tourists' needs. Hung, T.V. (2024) and Dong, T.Q. (2025) also analyzed and pointed out the limitations in developing tourism products, that although there are advantages in tourism development, they have not made a strong impression, have not created a breakthrough in developing cultural products for tourism development; It is necessary to create new cultural products and transform cultural products into products with economic and social value. Or, GN (2025) affirmed that tourism products of the Mekong Delta are not diverse and rich, have not

promoted the values and resources of unique culture and nature, and lack specific tourism products with the region's big brands.

The scales and observed variables have standard reliability test values, which are the basis for further analysis. The author conducts exploratory factor

analysis with Varimax rotation to preliminarily assess the unidimensionality, convergent value, and discriminant value of the scales to have more basis for drawing research conclusions about the suitability of the proposed theoretical research model (Table 3 and Table 4).

Table 3: Total Variance Explained.

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.767
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1738.745
	df	36
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance Explained									
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.778	41.978	41.978	3.778	41.978	41.978	2.637	29.305	29.305
2	2.686	29.845	71.823	2.686	29.845	71.823	2.607	28.969	58.274
3	1.197	13.303	85.127	1.197	13.303	85.127	2.417	26.853	85.127
4	.390	4.336	89.462						
5	.356	3.957	93.419						
6	.219	2.434	95.853						
7	.175	1.950	97.803						
8	.133	1.477	99.280						
9	.065	.720	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Source: Author's Survey Results

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix.

Rotated Component Matrix ^a				
Scales	Observed variables	Component		
		1	2	3
1. Natural, cultural and social conditions (NC)	NC1	.856		
	NC2	.860		
	NC3	.791		
2. Local policies (LP)	LP1		.891	
	LP2		.842	
	LP3		.812	
3. Developing tourism (DT)	DT1			.879
	DT2			.805
	DT3			.847

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
 a. Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

Source: Author's Survey Results

In terms of theory, exploratory factor analysis was performed in accordance with the data set shown through the values: $0.5 \leq KMO \leq 1$; Bartlett test with observation significance level $Sig. < 0.05$; Eigenvalue ≥ 1 ; Total Variance Explained $\geq 50\%$; Factor Loading ≥ 0.5 (Hair, J.F. et al., 2009).

Data in Table 3 and Table 4 show that:

- The $KMO = 0.767 > 0.5$, confirming that exploratory factor analysis is appropriate for the data set; Bartlett's test has an observed significance level of $Sig. = 0.000 < 0.05$, showing that the observed variables have a linear correlation with the representative factor. Total variance extracted

with Cumulative % = $85.127\% > 50\%$ (Table 3), showing that 85.127% of the variation of the representative factors is explained by the observed variables; all observed variables have Factor Loading > 0.5 (Table 4), showing that the observed variables have good statistical significance. The theoretical research model initially proposed is consistent with the survey research practice.

- The observed variables were extracted into 03 factors corresponding to 03 initial factors with Eigenvalues > 1 (Table 3), continuing to confirm the suitability of the initial research model. And the initial research model was kept intact, including: 02

independent variables "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) and 01 dependent variable "Developing tourism" (DT) with a total of 9 observed variables with good statistical significance, which can perform multivariate linear

regression analysis to examine the relationship of the scales in the model. The results of the regression analysis are shown in Table 5, which is the basis for the author to draw research conclusions.

Table 5: Multivariate Regression Results.

Coefficients ^a							
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	1.028	.241		11.302	.000	
	Natural, cultural and social conditions (NC)	.482	.318	.456	9.126	.000	1.813
	Local policies (LP)	.424	.293	.394	8.457	.000	1.829
a. Dependent Variable: Developing tourism (DT)							
R ² : 0.742; Durbin-Watson: 2.101							

Source: Author's Survey Results

The data in Table 5 shows that:

+ $R^2 = 0.742$, confirming that the scales "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) explain 74.2% of the variation in the scale "Tourism development" (DL); VIF = 1.813 and VIF = 1.829 ($1 < VIF < 2$), showing that the regression model does not have multicollinearity; Durbin-Watson = 2.101 ($1 < d < 3$), showing that the regression model does not have autocorrelation, confirming that the scales "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) are independent and have the same impact on the scale "Developing tourism" (DT), confirming the suitability of the theoretical research model with the survey data set.

+ The regression coefficients of the two independent variables "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) are both statistically significant Sig. = 0.000 (Sig. < 0.05) and have positive values: B (NC) = 0.482 and B (LP) = 0.424, confirming the positive relationship between the two independent variables "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (NC), "Local policies" (LP) and 01 dependent variable "Developing tourism" (DT); hypotheses H1, H2 are accepted; the initial research model continues to be confirmed to be appropriate. The multivariate regression model of this study is: $DT = 1.028 + 0.482*NC + 0.424*LP$. The correlation level of independent variables and dependent variables in decreasing order is: "Natural, cultural and social conditions" (TN), "Local policies" (CS).

From the above results of testing, analysis and evaluation, the research conclusion that the author is interested in is:

- Localities in the Mekong Delta have favorable natural, cultural and social conditions for tourism development; local policies are issued towards the conservation and exploitation of natural resource values, the exploitation of heritage values, environmental protection and the development of

human resources for the purpose of tourism development.

- In specific aspects, the conservation and exploitation of natural resource values, the exploitation of heritage values, environmental protection and the development of human resources for the purpose of tourism development have not been carried out with the expected results and efficiency: (1) Natural resources and heritages, ethnic and community cultures have been exploited, but there are still limitations in output - tourism products are not diverse and rich enough to meet the increasing needs of tourists; (2) Propaganda and education work has been implemented, but is still not effective in raising people's understanding, awareness and responsibility in the conservation of nature, the exploitation of ethnic and community heritages and cultures for the purpose of local tourism development.

The above issue has a direct impact on tourism development in the Mekong Delta. Because tourism products are exploited in a diverse way; people are educated regularly and fully, they will have knowledge and responsibility to protect nature, protect heritage, national culture, and community, at this time the localities will have favorable conditions to develop tourism.

From the research conclusion, the author discusses policy solutions to contribute to promoting tourism development in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, which are:

- Firstly, build strategies and implement policies to develop diverse tourism products. Localities invest in research and development of unique, diverse and in-depth tourism products: Policies to encourage research and creation of tourism products based on the unique cultural, historical and natural potential of the Mekong Delta; policies to develop diverse tourism products (cultural tourism, community tourism,

culinary tourism, rural tourism, sports tourism, etc.) to meet the increasing needs of tourists.

- Second, raise awareness of tourism and develop sustainable tourism. Localities develop and implement plans and programs to communicate and educate the community about the importance of sustainable tourism, the responsibility to preserve culture, protect the environment and tourism resources. From there, people regularly have access to information, improve their understanding and

REFERENCES

- Dong, T.Q. (2025). "Developing cultural products and services to promote Vietnam's image to the world". Communist Magazine, address https://tapchicongsan.org.vn/vi_VN/web/guest/gop-y-du-thao-cac-van-kien-trinh-dai-hoi-xiii-cua-dang/-/2018/818302/view_content, accessed on January 7, 2025.
- Duc, L.Q. (2012). "Cultural resources and the role of cultural resources in socio-economic development". Folklore Review, No. 4.
- GN - Government Newspaper (2025). "Tourism in the Mekong Delta: Why can't it take off yet", address <https://baochinhphu.vn/du-lich-dong-bang-song-cuu-long-vi-sao-chua-the-cat-canh-102250608084827249.htm>, June 8, 2025.
- Hair, J.F.; Black, W.C.; Babin, B.J.; Anderson, R.E. (2009). *Multivariate Data Analysis, 7th Edition*. Prentice Hall.
- Hong, N.M. (2025). "Solutions for sustainable tourism development in Vietnam". Journal of Economic and Forecast, address <https://kinhtevadubao.vn/giai-phap-phat-trien-du-lich-ben-vung-o-viet-nam-31549.html>, June 16, 2025.
- Hung, N.M. (2023). "Sustainable tourism development in Vietnam". Journal of Political Theory, address <https://lyluanchinhtri.vn/phat-trien-du-lich-ben-vung-o-viet-nam-5588.html>, February 24, 2023.
- Hung, T.V. (2024). "Developing cultural resources to meet the requirements of innovation and international integration". State Management Magazine, address <https://www.quanlynhanuoc.vn/2024/03/26/phat-trien-nguon-luc-van-hoa-dap-ung-yeu-cau-cua-cong-cuoc-doi-moi-va-hoi-nhap-quoc-te/>, March 26, 2024.
- Mai, T.T.X. (2017). "Tourism in the Mekong Delta: Potential and development solutions". Industry and Trade Magazine, address <https://tapchicongthuong.vn/du-lich-vung-dong-bang-song-cuu-long--tiem-nang-va-giai-phap-phat-trien-48421.htm>, July 11, 2017.
- Minh, L.V. (2022). "Factors affecting sustainable tourism development in the context of development". Institute for Tourism Development Research, address https://itdr.org.vn/nghien_cuu/cac-yeu-to-anh-huong-den-phat-trien-du-lich-ben-vung-trong-boi-can-phat-trien/, November 21, 2022.
- PN - Peoples' Newspaper (2005). "Overview of Vietnam's natural conditions", address <https://nhandan.vn/khai-quat-ve-dieu-kien-tu-nhien-nuoc-viet-nam-post522067.html>, April 14, 2005.
- Thu, N.T.H. (2025). "Policy for sustainable tourism development in Vietnam". Journal of Industrial and Commercial Research, address <https://vioit.vn/chinh-sach-phat-trien-du-lich-theo-huong-ben-vung-tai-viet-nam.html>, date November 1, 2025.
- Ung, N.T. (2025). "Sustainable tourism development in Vietnam from a social perspective: Current situation, issues and solutions". Communist Review, address <https://www.tapchicongsan.org.vn/web/guest/tinh-ninh-binh/-/2018/1145502/phat-trien-du-lich-ben-vung-o-viet-nam-tu-phuong-dien-xa-hoi---thuc-trang%2C-van-de-dat-ra-va-giai-phap.aspx#>, September 15, 2025.
- VNA - Vietnam National Assembly (2017). Law on Tourism 09/2017/QH14, dated June 19, 2017.
- VNAT - Vietnam National Authority of Tourism (2025). "Tourism in the Mekong Delta: Developing tourism to adapt to the new situation", address <https://vietnamtourism.gov.vn/post/61647>, March 7, 2025.
- Wikipedia (2025). "Tourism", address https://vi.wikipedia.org/wiki/Du_lich, August 9, 2025.

awareness, and personal responsibility in preserving nature, exploiting heritage, ethnic culture, and community for the purpose of developing local tourism.

Acknowledgement: All authors have made contributions for this research and agreed to the published version of the manuscript. The authors declare no conflict of interest. This research is funded by University of Finance - Marketing, Vietnam.